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LAND USE LAND COVER CLASSIFICATION USING ARC-GIS AND ERDAS TOOL - A REVIEW

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Abstract:

In India rapidly growing urban population has become cause of worry among the country 's urban and town planners for organized urban planning. The substantially growing urban areas have led to sharp land use land cover changes. With the remote sensing technology Land-Cover/Land-use, concept is taken as a decisive item of necessary tasks in order to execute a series of significant works, such as predicting land-use change, preventing natural calamity, managing and planning of land use, protecting surroundings, etc. Accurate and dependable information over land use and land cover is required to detect changes and to monitor the required area. The geographical information related to any area can also be updated using this. a considerable amount of research has been conducted over the past years, regarding the application of different classifier and image fusion technique. In order to obtain reliable and latest information on the temporal, spatial and structural change in forest cover and to appreciate the connection between the current development and its likely impact on land cover/land use and environment of the required area, the variations in the attribution of total area into various specific land cover/ use classes have been studied.

Keywords: Land use, Land cover, Urban, GIS, Remote Sensing.

Introduction:

Urbanization is an essential part of modern world but it is also playing a sideways influence of economic growth of any country. India, being a developing country, urbanization makes a major contribution in its economic growth. In India, all the towns and cities have developed slowly during the nineteenth and the twentieth century's. Urbanization is considered as an inevitable process due to rapidly growing population and

economic expansion. Intrusion into urban settlements founded on agricultural lands may present ruinous effects such as dreadful conditions and desertification of land (Shalaby et al, 2004). The rapid growth of population in the recent years is been determined mainly near metropolitan and new cities.

In order to obtain reliable and latest formation on the temporal, spatial and structural change in forest area and to appreciate the connection between the current development and its likely impact on land cover/land use and total environment of the region, the variations in the attribution of total area into various specific land cover/ use classes have been studied.

The rapidly developing idea of the vegetation mapping is believed to have lead to increased studies over land use and land cover change globally. The actual definitions of land use and land cover are quite distinct. Land use refers to, “man’s activities on land which are directly related to the land” (Singh, A. 1989). Land cover on the other hand describes, “the vegetation and artificial constructions covering the land surface” (Lins et al,1996).

Land-cover gives importance particularly to its nature properties and it is the reflection of various rudiments in global surface covered with manual construction or natural body. Remote sensing classification method, has its speciality of separating whatever used or non-used covering object in the surface. Reconstruction activities that human adopts such as series of biological, and technological measure to manage and regulate the land chronically and periodically depending on economic and social purpose has brought land use to emphasize more on land’s social properties. Thus, land-use is taken as a procedure of converting natural ecology into communal ecology. (Swapan and Rajiv, 2012).

A modern nation is required to have accurate information regarding many complex interconnected aspects of its proceedings in order to make healthy decisions. Knowledge regarding land use and land cover has eventually become important as it helps nation in planning to overcome the problems of undirected uncontrolled development, declining ecological quality, depletion of primary agricultural lands, desolation of swamp, and diminution of fish and wildlife environment (Anderson et al, 1976).

Legislators, planners and state and local government officials use the information related to present distribution and agricultural area, recreational and urban lands as well as information on their changing proportions in order to decide better land use policy, to plan transportation and utility demand, to recognize future development pressure points and areas, and to implement effective plans for regional development. As Singh,A. (1989) have declared: In this forceful condition, adequate and relevant data on land use are necessary.

Applications of land use and land cover data is found to be extremely vast. In many states grading of tax assessments is done with the help of land use and land cover data. It is also required by agencies of local, state and federal in the field of water resources in order to control flood and planning of water supply with waste water treatment. Management of public lands is being improved by many central agencies by using the informations of ongoing activities on public lands accomodated with the existing and changing uses of vicinal private lands. Land use data also helps to study impact caused on environment resulting from the rapidly developing energy resources, in order to handle wildlife resources and to reduce man-wildlife conflicts emerging in ecosystem, to detect land

use patterns and changes which further helps in formulation of national policy and to evaluate the upcoming impacts on environmental quality.

Land use classification

A number of methods have been invented for land use classification which is well-known as unsupervised and supervised classification. Land use classification can be done either by an unsupervised method where the groups are formed by their relative connection, or by a supervised method based on similarity of cases to obtain predefined classes that have been characterized spectrally. Unsupervised classification is the process to identify natural groups, or structures, within multispectral data. Supervised classification is done by using training samples, of known identity to classify pixels of unknown identity.

Temporal crop and land use inventory was prepared by using a supervised classification approach. GIS aided arrangement was used to carry cropping pattern study of temporal crop recorded information. Land use matching process consist of examining obstructions and arranging them according to their contribution with proper weight age and considering the options of making improvements. The skilled classification system used to classify the dominant land cover types as (23%) cultivated vegetation, (16%) high density urban, (10%) cultivated land without vegetation, and (9%) undeveloped based on skilled classification system earlier made for the Phoenix urban area using Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM) imagery (Swapan and Rajiv, 2012).

Literature Review:

Exact and up-to-date information on land cover change is necessary to understand and assess the environmental effects of such changes (Giri et al, 2005) while remote sensing has the ability to capture such changes and to extract information related to changes from satellite data which requires efficient and automated change detection techniques (Roy et al,2002).

Many studies shown land cover and land use changes in arid, semi-arid and agricultural productive land. Study conducted by Lambin and Ehrlich (1977) used 10 years (1982-1991) of daily, continental-scale satellite remote sensing data to analyze changes in land cover magnitude. Deviations were measured and mapped for every year. The study's results demonstrated that continuous uni-directional alteration processes affected less than 4% of Sub-Saharan Africa during study period.

A comprehensive attempt was made by Rembold et al (2000) to study the land cover changes in lake regions of central/south Ethiopia using aerial photographs of 1972 and 1994 Landsat image. From the analysis it was noted that there was a general trend of increase in fertilized surfaces. Expansion of wasteland was also recognized and rapidly reactivated erosion in newly cropped areas were observed.

The study of the temporal changes of spatial patterns in cultural landscape is marked as important in order to understand the concealed factors and functional influences. A comprehensive attempt was made by Mendoza and Etter (2002) to monitor land cover changes using collective black and white aerial photographs that covered 56 years (1940-1996) in parts of Bogota, Colombia. After analysis, the changes in natural forest found were small with opposite trends in study sites. The plantation forests had been steadily increasing in both sites and area of crop and pasture covers showed opposite complementary trends.

The study was conducted by Palmer et al (2002) to explore the vastness and direction and magnitude land use change in reflectance using two study areas in southern Kalhari desert from 1989 to 1994. The results after analysis showed the increase in infrared activity on active dunes near water points on profitable farms since 1989.

A comprehensive attempt was made by Ram and Kolarkar (1993) to study land use changes identified in various parts of Rajasthan and were mapped by surveying and getting , semi-detailed and detailed levels using multirate remotely sensed data, followed by with field checks and secondary informations. The results showed that during last three decades the net sown area had increased by 36percent.

In Egypt, agricultural production was, limited by violation of urban settlements and soil salinity onto previously cultivated lands. So a study was conducted by Lenney et al (1996) using field-calibrated, multi temporal NDVI (normalized difference vegetation index) feature derived from 10 Landsat TM images dating from 1984 to 1993 to explore the standing of agricultural land in Egypt. The results indicated a high rate of repossession in the period 1986–1993 and low rate of conversion from agricultural productive lands in urban areas between 1984 to 1990.

A comprehensive attempt was made by Dewan et al (2009) in Greater Dhaka Bangladesh, between 1975 and 2003 for analyzing urban expansion and land cover changes using satellite images and socio-economic data. Spatial and temporal dynamics of land use cover changes were evaluated using these Landsat images, a supervised classification algorithm and the post classification changes detection technique in GIS. Remote sensing data provided valuable multi-temporal data on the processes and patterns of LULC change, and with the help of GIS these patterns were mapped and analyzed. Analysis discovered that there was increase in urban areas from 1975 to 2003, which further led to considerable reduction in the water bodies areas, vegetation, cultivated areas and wetlands/lowland. Land use maps developed in this study contributed to development of sustainable urban.

Li et al (2004) conducted a study using GIS and Remote Sensing in the Pearl River delta of south china to analyze magnitude and direction of urban expansion and spatial restructuring of land use patterns. Land use changes over 1933-1988 and 1933-1997 were analyzed to display how the direction and magnitude of landscape change was influenced by enforcing land use policies. Spatial patterns measurements were determined by using the compactness index and entropy. Three major types of land use changes were detected—change from agricultural land to built-up areas and development sites, conversion from cropland to fishpond, and change of cropland to orchard. These types of land use changes contributed about 88.0% of the total changes in the Pearl River Delta during 1988–1993. The largest figure found was of the agricultural land loss which contributed about 7.7% of the total land or 13.1% of the total agricultural land.

A study was conducted by Buhaug et al (2013) for investigating how patterns of public unrest in urban areas were influenced by population growth within the context of crucial prime factors like democracy, poverty, and economic stocks, as migration from rural to urban areas was taken as major cause of man-wildlife conflict. It utilized a disturbance covering 55 major cities in Asia and sub-Saharan Africa since 1960. The experimental analysis provided little support for the notion that high and increasing urban population pressure leads to a higher risk of social disorder.

So far many techniques have been developed to detect and trace differences (e.g. image differencing, ratios or correlation) and these might be attributable to change (Singh, 1989; Stow et al 1996; Yuan et al 1999). However, the simple detection of change is rarely sufficient in itself: information is generally required about the initial and final land cover or types or land uses, the “from-to” analysis (Khorram et al.,1999).

Conclusion:

Land use and land cover changes contributes its major part in the study of global change. Land use/ Land cover and human/natural modifications have led to deforestation, biodiversity loss, global warming and constant increase of natural disaster flooding. Therefore available data on LULC changes can provide critical input which further helps in making decision for ecological management and planning the future.

Pressure created by rapid growth of population and increasing socio economic necessities has resulted in accidental and unrestrained changes in LULC. Misconduct of agricultural, urban and range of forest lands caused alteration in land use land cover which led to severe environmental problems such as landslides, floods etc.

Existing literature demonstrated that progress has been made in identifying the potential consequences of various land changes, though there remains a clear need to improve the tools available to predict and manage specific impacts of land use and land cover change.

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